

Formation and Development of a New System of Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan in the Globalization

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Abstract—The concept of the new government should focus on forming a new relationship between public servants and citizens of the state, formed on the principles of transparency, accountability, protection of citizens' rights. These principles are laid down in the problem of administrative reform in the Republic of Kazakhstan. Also, this wish arises, contributing to the improvement of the system of political management in our country. For the full realization of the goals is necessary to develop a special state program designed to improve the regulatory framework for public service, improving training, retraining and advanced training of civil servants, forming a system of incentives in public service and other activities aimed at achieving the efficiency of the entire system government.

Keywords—Kazakhstan, political management, independence

I. INTRODUCTION

THE Republic of Kazakhstan announced independence on December 16, 1991, and for over 20 years, is building the state, because during the period of entry into the Soviet Union, Russian Empire, the state bodies of Kazakhstan were purely nominal. Study of the problems of formation and use in Kazakhstan's political system and methods of political management is an important task for the national political science and practice. Legal terms of development of political management were laid down by the Constitution of the Republic of Kazakhstan, which declared the establishment of the country's democratic constitutional state, which is characterized by widespread use in the activities of not only government, but the socio-political management practices to address the emerging society of conflicts and contradictions. The old model of political control, by virtue of objective and subjective factors, was completely dismantled and a new promising model of political management has not yet become dominant. This is what caused interest in the issues of improved governance on the basis of political management and the formation of fundamentally new relations between state bodies and civil society.

II. STATE MANAGEMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBALIZATION

In the current context of global risks and challenges to put on the agenda of issues develop qualitatively new approaches to the formation of strengthening the foundations of public administration. The system of governance can not be regarded as a set of sectors that have their own development objectives and principles of autonomous regulation.

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Essential common principles and approaches that strengthen the foundation of governance and form the basis of the economy as a whole.

Today the government has changed dramatically, significantly complicated management problems, increased demands on the efficiency and effectiveness of management decisions that increased the role of the analytical component in the activities of government.

At the present stage of development is changing the purpose of the qualitative features of the state. In the current transformation process to state regulation played a fundamental role, installed content and direction of the global economy. Despite the abundance of discussions and opinions in the scientific community regarding the place and role of government in the new economic system, most researchers agree that in the short-term economic development will require substantial interference of state bodies, because it is the government establish a national fund of knowledge.

The concept of New Public Management - Public Management - emerged in the 1990s as a theoretical basis conducted in the West of administrative reforms. The principal difference from the traditional concept is that it provides for the introduction of innovations in the process of decision making, building partnerships and accounting ethics component in the government. According to the theory of new public management ideas, beliefs, values, identity and trust, and cooperation and collaboration are becoming an integral feature of the management. "The public administration in general, the bureaucracy is not seen as mere implementing a policy-making, as well as participants in decision-making and to find effective models for their implementation [1]." In such a system increases the responsibility of government officials and the organization of public service. In analyzing the recent developments of the new challenges of public administration in management theory, it should be emphasized that in recent years, more attention is paid to the efficiency of public governance as a key element of this concept within different organizational cultures. Each type of organizational culture defines the criteria for organizational performance and managerial style of leadership. To be effective in dealing with administrative tasks necessary to choose behaviors that adequate dominant culture of the organization as a management activity not only influences the development of culture of the organization, but also its product. In modern politics, many discussions about the effectiveness - it is really arguing about what values the government should pursue. "In those situations where we are willing to share resources and goals, we can determine how to maximize the effectiveness of comprehension of our objectives through the use of limited resources. That is what the term has the most relevance to the traditional control theory [2]"

One of the most important factors in forming a new government is to consider the geopolitical, geographical and natural-resource-economic conditions of the state.

The importance of resource supply is shown clearly in the evaluation of managerial effort and solved similar problems in different contexts. Factors and conditions of the resource (in the broadest sense) in the provision of this until recently in the judgment of many influential politicians and scientists have been omitted. Meanwhile, in the modern geography of the notion of “effective area” - one that is suitable for long-term human habitation. For this indicator, Kazakhstan, like many CIS countries, yields in Brazil, USA, Australia and China. In addition, the “effective area” has its gradations, depending on the climate, the vastness of the territory, etc. For example, to achieve well-being of Western Europeans, the Russians need each spend on average three times more energy [3]. Naturally, the comparative mapping of political elites of various countries is necessary to introduce a correction factor that takes into account environmental and resource security.

Recently, the importance of environmental factors have become more careful to look closely [4]. In addition, the actual practice of inclusion in the market of international relations clearly confirms this, and forced to consider not only the internal features, but also environmental factors.

Along with the natural and geographical conditions, is largely a framework of opportunities and priorities of the government in the development, the importance of internal organizational factors, high government and management in building an effective policy.

Since internally the system of public administration may be presented as a subject-object interaction, it is regarded as the subject itself is structural and functional layout of the named system. The object appears society. In some respects, this layout requires a revision of traditional notions of government organizations, where people, represent the society as the supreme and final authority, and implies that he has delegated the operational and administrative functions of the state apparatus. However, the practice of state activity often shows evidence realization of delegated powers in a distorted form.

As another perspective, a significant impact on the effectiveness of government, it is associated with the horizontal distribution of powers between different branches of government: legislative, executive and judicial. The main problems of inefficiency in this vein are associated with a lack of organization of each branch and their interaction with each other. Meanwhile, the operation of each branch can be estimated relatively independently in terms of its level of efficiency and performance according to its basic functions [5].

The management component of political power is measured by its degree of organization and efficiency. Naturally, the political impact of different social, economic, spiritual and connected primarily with the degree of achievement nominated by political goals and objectives and the implementation of the basic functions of political power. If the realization of political aims we have observed a significant

deviation or visible dysfunction, then we should speak of the ineffectiveness of political power.

If the value aspect of the efficiency of power is largely derived from the subjective-environmental factors of its operation, the management aspect is related to the objective-function of its manifestations. Political and managerial effectiveness depends on the level and completeness of the implementation of such basic functions as the protection of public order, prevention and elimination of dangerous social conflict and social tension, control of economic and social relations, the implementation of national programs of economic and financial, cultural, scientific, educational development; solution to the problems of social protection and safety of citizens, the implementation of foreign policy and defense functions.

It should be noted that this aspect of performance in today's society is emerging as the resulting organized by the interaction of different levels and branches of political and state power. Efficiency is influenced by the balance of power at the national, regional and local levels.

In states where this balance is in favor of a national level, with insufficient development of self-government is overheating at this level and gradually bogged down in an increasing amount of social and economic problems. In addition, the volume increases and paternalistic expectations. On the other hand, the transfer of significant powers to regional and local levels for staffing and lack of managerial skills and the absence of thorough legal framework creates the effect of powerlessness authorities in the implementation of socio-economic functions and provide internal security. Both are in the process we are witnessing a new system of political power in Kazakhstan.

Evaluating the effectiveness of public administration is necessary for both public authorities and society as a whole, first because it allows to improve the management process, and the public can monitor the quality of public institutions. The central problem in assessing the effectiveness of public administration is the choice of criteria. The criteria for the effectiveness of government is chosen feature or combination of features, which are estimated on the basis of performance management system as a whole, as well as individual management decisions. Actually, the process evaluation of the effectiveness of public administration points to the social significance of certain events (social and natural). The objects of evaluation results can serve a variety of management activities: subsistence, types of social relations, processes, and specific acts of others, referred to as “substantive values.” The objects are estimated, ie, determined by their social significance, in accordance with the priorities, principles, objectives, concepts, rules implemented by the state at a particular time policy.

Each political system characterized by its own system and the hierarchy of values, the basics of being objectively determined the state and the public interest. The value system is the fruit of the collective creativity of the historic community of people, reflecting the result of interaction with the environment of the political community, and social

relationships among its members. The value system of a particular political union (the state) does not cover all their diversity that exists in the social world (eg, moral, aesthetic, scientific, political, etc.). It is composed of the most significant for the existence and functioning of the political union of values, which are enshrined in the constitutional foundations of the political system, ideology, political principles and objectives of the state, embodied in political strategy as well as the principles, concepts and objectives of the control subject. As the core values of any modern state, including Kazakhstan, are: political democracy (democracy), the sovereignty of the state, its integrity and security, legal, law, political and social rights and freedoms, free labor, based on the diversity of ownership of the means of production, pluralism etc. In addition, millions of Kazakhstan recognizes many other traditional values such as social justice, spirituality, and the preservation of national traditions, etc. All these should be included in the criteria for determining the effectiveness of the main activities of the state. Formulated by the ruling elites and political leaders, proven historical experience and the basic values enshrined the right take on significant, objective in relation to members of society and to the control subjects. The smaller the gap between the officially proclaimed values and the regulations of "play" control, the real effectiveness of management.

To realize the vision of a new government in the Republic of Kazakhstan in the current conditions there are a number of assumptions. First, set up legal and regulatory framework that meets international standards: the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On local government in the Republic of Kazakhstan" (2001) Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On State Service" (2003) Presidential Decree on 13.01.2007 "On measures to modernize the public administration of the Republic of Kazakhstan" Presidential Address to the people of Kazakhstan "New Kazakhstan in a New World", the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On making amendments and additions, and to some legislative acts of the Republic of Kazakhstan on improvement of administrative Procedures" (2007) and other regulations in the field of public administration and public service. This package of documents aimed at improving governance in Kazakhstan can also supplement approved in 2006 by the Presidential Decree "Concept of Transition of Kazakhstan to Sustainable Development for 2007-2024." Which as a political basis for sustainable development (Section 3.2) denotes the "improvement of democratic processes, the consistent expansion of the role of democracy as a mechanism for accounting for majority and minority opinions in decision making at all levels of government [6]. " This lays the groundwork for expanding the priority of public participation in governance, which is one of the most important principles of the new government. However, along with the full realization of the concept in our country need to implement a number of institutional reforms.

III. RECOMMENDATIONS

First of all, you need to concentrate on the Government of the comprehensive evaluation of the effectiveness of public administration. Theoretical and methodological studies in the

framework of the Academy of Public Administration under the President [7] suggest that the evaluation of the effectiveness of public administration can be done through: 1) analysis of the implementation of government, industry and budget programs, 2) assess the quality of public services to individuals and legal persons, and 3) evaluation of the effectiveness of public authority.

In 2005 the Ministry of Economy and Budget Planning of Kazakhstan have developed the concepts and proposals for system evaluation of the effectiveness and quality of public authorities, but they have not been approved and now require the improvement and revision. It seems that a lot of work to be done (by the example of many developed countries such as USA, New Zealand) under the patronage of the Government by creating a consortium with the participation of leading national scholars, experts and government officials themselves. Thus, evaluation of the effectiveness of government, providing for the development of methods for measuring the factors that have a significant impact on the effectiveness of government should be the basis of the new government.

The next important component of the concept of the new government should be to improve education, training and retraining of managers. The key areas of change in this unit can offer the following:

- Training of civil servants should be done on a regular basis and cover all categories on the basis of horizontal and vertical;
- Special attention should be paid to the context of control theory with practice, ie, increasing the value of the formation of knowledge and skills in project design and predictive;
- Learning the specifics of the use of management techniques in a variety of organizational forms;
- The formation of lasting interest to educate themselves, the responsibility for learning outcomes;
- Assessing the skills of management, its effectiveness and efficiency;
- The skills of innovative thinking, receptivity to innovation;
- Knowledge of diplomatic protocol, ethics, and negotiation;
- The acquisition of leadership skills and teamwork.

IV. CONCLUSION

Summing up the political analysis conducted by the process of formation and development of a new government in the Republic of Kazakhstan, we have made such a conclusion. In general, the concept of the new government should focus on forming a new relationship between public servants and citizens of the state, formed on the principles of transparency, accountability, protection of citizens' rights. These principles are laid down in the problem of administrative reform in the Republic of Kazakhstan.

Also, this wish arises, contributing to the improvement of the system of political management in our country. For the full realization of the goals is necessary to develop a special state program designed to improve the regulatory framework for

public service, improving training, retraining and advanced training of civil servants, forming a system of incentives in public service and other activities aimed at achieving the efficiency of the entire system government.

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